

The Moderating Effect of Openness to Experience on the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Competency of Teachers

Author's Details:

⁽¹⁾Ma. Lenora Theresa S. Ibacarra, EdD, Department of Education, Davao City, Philippines ⁽²⁾Rinante L. Genuba, EdD, University of Mindanao, Davao City, Philippines

Abstract

The ultimate aim of this study is to determine the moderating effect of openness to experience on the relationship between emotional intelligence and teaching competency of teachers in Caraga Region. Adapted survey questionnaires were given to a sample of 400 teachers from various schools in the region. Findings revealed that the level of emotional intelligence is high, teaching competency is very high and the level of openness to experience is high. Further, findings revealed that emotional intelligence is significantly related to teaching competency, emotional intelligence also showed a positive significant relationship to teaching competency. To determine the moderating effect of openness to experience, a logistic hierarchical regression was employed in this study. Results revealed that openness to experience demonstrated a significant moderating effect on the relationship between emotional intelligence and teaching competency. Teachers who have higher openness to experience have higher level of emotional intelligence and teaching competency. With these three Constructs as support system, superior performance and competitiveness among the teachers may be expected.

Keywords: education, openness to experience, emotional intelligence, teaching competency, Philippines

INTRODUCTION

Most scholars and researchers use the concept of 'teaching competency' as synonymous with 'teaching quality' or 'teaching excellence' (Shepard, Harland, Stein, & Tidswell, 2011; Woody, 2010; King & Watson, 2010; McKenzie, 2007; Moore & Nyiel, 2007; Palmer & Coldwell, 2000). Teaching competency is determined by the capability of faculty to successfully perform all of the functions required by their professions in a manner that corresponds to the teaching quality traits that we have derived from the official documents in the previous sections of this paper. Since the 1920s, the issue of educator's capabilities, which can ensure their teaching competency, has been of worry for the art of Pedagogy, as well as for those responsible for staffing schools with qualified experts (Liakopoulou, 2011). Sometimes, the problems in teaching competency happened because of outer factors, for example, visit supervision and intercession of the central into the classroom instructing, the absence of finding solutions from principals with respect to the new educational programs change, absence of help and support from the directors and guardians . (Erden, 2010).

Furthermore, teaching competency, means that giving effective feedback can better develop critical thinking skills (Thiessen, 2011). Assessing teaching competency of the understudy/ instructor /educator getting expanding consideration in the Educational people group and this much consideration is essentially because of the significance of educators readiness and the part they play in the public eye. Teacher's competency intermittently as indicated by a logical report is one of the essential components that decide the fundamental reasons prompt lacks in instructors' amplexness which retrains them to create showing competency weak side (Al-Sharif, 2010). Recognizing the importance of teaching competency as discussed in the preceding paragraph, the researcher conducted an intensive review of literature that may affect or moderate teaching competency. A number of related literature showed the link between emotional intelligence and teaching competency (Khatkar, Sangwan, & Bedi, 2016), likewise it was also established that openness to experience is associated with teaching competency (Neubert, 2004). According to Al-Sharif, (2010) Execution utilizing competency is a standout amongst the most imperative intends to innovative advancements that have risen of late in instructive field as response to disappointment with instructor which prompted rise of readiness by execution or competency educator planning approach in light of competency depends in change between and errands required from educator of the competency ought to be aced by understudy/educator before graduation.

It is in the above context that the researcher decided to conduct the study with the intention of determining which of the above-mentioned variables may have direct effect or may moderate the effect of one variable. Although there are already existing literature on the association between emotional intelligence and teaching competency and so with openness to experience and teaching competency, this study dealt only with bivariate relationship and did not cover the three variables in a single study. This study dealt with the three variables with one variable as the moderating construct making this study a contribution to the new knowledge.

Objective of the Study

The study was conducted to determine the moderating effect of openness to experience on the relationship between emotional intelligence and teacher competence in Caraga Region.

Specifically, the following objectives are formulated:

1. To assess the level of emotional intelligence of the teachers in terms of:
 - 1.1 self-awareness;
 - 1.2 self-regulation;
 - 1.3 motivation ;
 - 1.4 empathy; and
 - 1.5 social skills
2. To ascertain the level of teaching competency of the teachers in terms of:
 - 2.1 planning;
 - 2.2 presentation;
 - 2.3 closing;
 - 2.4 evaluation; and
 - 2.5 managerial.
3. To determine the level of openness to experience.
4. To determine the significance of relationship between:
 - 4.1 emotional intelligence and teaching competency;
 - 4.2 openness to experience and teaching competency.
5. To find out the significance of moderating effect of openness to experience on the relationship between emotional intelligence and teaching competency of teachers.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Emotional Intelligence

Truly, the term EI was presented in 1990 by two American University educators Mayer and Salovey in their endeavours to build up a logical measure for knowing the distinctions in individuals' capacity in the zones of feelings. Be that as it may, the credit for advancing the idea of EI goes to another to another American Psychologist, Daniel Goleman (1995). Goleman has been to a great extent in charge of the far reaching advancement of term "Emotional Intelligence" through the production of his books. Goleman has shaped his own general hypothesis of EI in the light of illustration together his perceptions and ends from crafted by different researchers.

Emotional intelligence is the limit with regards to perceiving our own particular sentiments and those of others, for rousing ourselves, and for overseeing feelings well in ourselves and in our connections (Goleman, 1998). Individuals who can ready to investigate sentiments and non-verbal code are smarter to alter themselves inwardly, more prominent, less demanding to cooperate, and more delicate (Goleman, 2006).

Moreover, teachers feel really passionate about how things are done and feel totally engaged with their work. This is in consonance with the findings of Mortiboys (2005), which cited there are sure qualities of a sincerely clever instructor that can be identified. An instructor dedicates a lot of vitality to make an empowering climate in the classroom and considers the students emotions. (Into & Gempes, 2018) Untold stories of teachers wit multiple ancillary function. He or she ought to be a specialist at tuning in; pay attention to the learner's expectations; devotion to learner's excitement in the showing procedure and apply a remarkable way to deal with their calling to have the capacity to set up an amicable association with their understudies.

The proposition of Edannur (2010) which posited that emotional intelligence of educators is required with the goal

that learning happens ideally and enhances to the most extreme learning. One marker of Emotional Intelligence is *self-awareness*. Emotional awareness implies getting to be 100% mindful of your feelings so that you generally know why you are feeling terrible or encountering some other feeling regardless of whether you can't make a move . This implies that emotional self-awareness precedes all stages of emotional intelligence developmental ability and could be the basic foundation which behavior germinates and that one's own emotions recognizing their impact to guide decision (Singh, 2010). Emotional intelligence is the initial step required towards disposing of any terrible inclination that visits you. All things considered, you should know about the nearness of a feeling so as to have the capacity to dispose of it. The emotional intelligence includes the components, for example, mindfulness, sympathy, administration association, overseeing feels, and inspiration (Goleman, 2006).

Emotional management includes important skills such important skills as understand, control, and modify own emotions and feelings but also allows to be better understand how another person feels. Emotional management is required for diving in an emotional universe which is full of feelings and emotions (Olmedo & Gempes), Shaken but unruffled very varied as envy, anger, resentment, suffering, hope, peace, of mind, serenity, joy. Emotional awareness implies knowing when feeling are available in ourselves as well as other people. It is firmly identified with enthusiastic proficiency, which implies having the capacity to mark emotions with particular words. At its largest amount it implies having the capacity to anticipate sentiments ahead of time.

Relationship Management incorporates the distinguishing proof, examination, and administration of associations with individuals inside and outside of the group and also their advancement through criticism and training. It likewise fuses the capacity to impart, convince, and lead others, while being immediate and legitimate without estranging individuals. Pradhan, Mathur and Mishra (2001) detailed that emotional education is decidedly identified with general wellbeing and personal satisfaction. (Gempes & Sudaria, 2012) Satisfaction Domains of Rural Bank Individuals high on passionate proficiency abilities keep up better wellbeing and have a positive personal satisfaction. In spite of the fact that the improvement of enthusiastic knowledge is a characteristic procedure, yet it very well may be upgraded as it has been presumed that passionate insight can be educated and it ought to be a part of administration preparing reported that emotional literacy is positively related to general health and quality of life. People high on emotional literacy skills maintain better health and have a positive quality of life. Though the development of emotional intelligence is a natural process, yet it can be enhanced as it has been concluded that emotional intelligence can be learned and it should be a component of leadership training (Weisinger, 1998; Kaur & Talwar, 2014).

In addition, Mortiboys (2005) referred to that there are sure qualities of a sincerely smart instructor which can be specified. Such an instructor gives a lot of vitality to making an empowering climate in the classroom and considers the students' emotions. (Bernaldes & Gempes, 2016) Mediating Effect of Conflict of Management Style he or she ought to be a specialist at tuning in; also, they should focus on the students' desires. A viable instructor can be related with dedication to students, energy in the showing procedure, a remarkable way to deal with their calling in order to have the capacity to set up an amicable association with their understudies. Clearly, relational characteristics consider and descriptive words such: empathic, agreeable, and identifying with understudies as equivalents, can be specified too (Goad, 2005; Justice, 2005; Dhull, & Mangal, 2005; Kaur & Talwar, 2014).

Teaching Competency

Instructors are the foundation of each country. Each general public relies upon instructors for the advancement of their lives. It is instructors who can shape the entire world. However, instructors ought to be sufficiently equipped to come up to the desires for the general public (Ganaie & Mudasir, 2014). The term 'competency' is cited as a depiction of those exhibitions that depend on the obtaining, incorporation, composite building and use of an arrangement of related ability and learning. The qualities of competency are enthusiasm, fluency, industry, neatness, originality, adaptability and thrift. At the end of the day, it implies a coveted nature of employment execution. As per Encyclopaedic Dictionary of Education (1997), fitness implies as "the

condition of having and showing abilities and capacities or aptitudes in the agreeable execution of a learning assignment (Pratibha, 2017). Moreover, the words of Ganaie and Mudasir (2014) who mentioned in their study that teachers can shape the entire world but teachers be sufficiently skillful to think of the desire for the general public. One indicator of teaching competency is *planning*. Rana (2013) said that teaching competency includes teaching behavior and teaching skills. Teaching behaviors can be linked with knowledge of the subject matter and its presentation. The teacher acquires that knowledge through his continuous efforts and learns presentation during their training which determines his effectiveness. As indicated by Darling-Hammond (1999), educators with under three years' experience are less productive than are associates with more understanding. Following five years the extra commitment weakens. Andrew and Schwab (1995) noticed that unpracticed instructors from long educator training projects can be as proficient as experienced educators. Instructors' age may likewise be of significance for viability however this variable is obviously exceptionally connected with involvement. Teaching competency in the realm of the ESHE is determined by the capability of faculty to successfully perform all of the functions required by their professions in a manner that corresponds to the teaching quality traits. Thus, a skilful professor should possess specific skills in his/her specific area of expertise and in the didactic, communicative, and innovative realms (Valcárcel, Cases, & de Castro, 2003). These skills can be framed in the four realms: cognitive, functional, personal and ethical skills (Villa & Poblete, 2007). Also, Barr (1952) remarked, "Teacher effectiveness is a relationship between teachers, pupils and other persons concerned with the educational understanding. Teaching competency is a combination of traditional ideas that were propounded by the great educators in the past on one hand and at the new ideas like- systematic approach to education on the other hand".

Openness to Experience

Openness to experience is an idea officially utilized in mental evaluation in the Big Five model. Experiential psychotherapies have utilized it beginning with Carl Rogers, thinking of it as an asset that keeps a man solid (Cucu-Ciuhan & Raban- Motounu, 2012). Based from the Big Five identity show, openness to experience is one of the five noteworthy areas which are utilized to depict human identity. It includes dynamic creative energy, stylish affectability, mindfulness to internal sentiments, inclination for assortment, and scholarly interest (McCrae, 1993-1994).

In some studies (Gempes, 2008, Kaufman, 2013, Swami, and Furnham 2014) they expressed that individuals high in openness to feelings encounter a more extensive scope of feelings, acknowledge their feelings and experience complex feelings all the more frequently. Furthermore, Menninghaus, Wagner, Hanich and Jacobsen (2014) expressed that a man who is high in openness to experience is imaginative, adaptable, inquisitive and brave. He appreciates having his psyche and faculties animated, for example, by review craftsmanship, tuning in to new music, inspecting outlandish cooking and perusing writing and verse.

The quality recognizes inventive individuals from sensible, ordinary individuals. Individuals who score low on openness are thought to be shut to understanding. They incline toward natural schedules to new encounters, and by and large have a smaller scope of interests. Openness connected decidedly with the development and self-heading esteems composites, and contrarily with the accomplishment and prohibitive congruity composites. Results recommend that, more than alternate measurements of identity, openness to experience best records for what individuals esteem in their lives (Dollinger, Leong, & Ulicni, 1996).

Openness to experience—one of the significant culturally diverse components of identity (McCrae & Sutin, 2009) — sits at the focal point of the brain science of style, inventiveness, and expressions of the human experience. Individuals high in openness to experience appreciate stylish encounters, live more imaginative lives, and seek after and bolster expressions of the human experience. Individuals low in openness to experience, interestingly, is more ordinary, common sense, and practical (Conner & Silvia, 2015; Kaufman, 2013; Nettle, 2009; Swami & Furnham, 2014). Receptiveness to encounter is a perplexing, heterogeneous attribute. Generally, the nature of the other main considerations of identity are moderately uncontroversial (Ashton et al., 2014).

RESEARCH MODEL

Below is the research model of the study. It shows the relationship between the variables of the study. The moderating variable is the *openness to experience* by McCrae and Costa (2008) with the following facets, herein referred to as indicators namely: *fantasy*, which refers to receptivity to the inward universe of creative energy; *style*, which alludes to valuation for workmanship and excellence; *sentiments*, which alludes to receptiveness to internal emotions and feelings; *activities*, which alludes to openness to new experiences on a useful level; *thoughts*, which alludes to scholarly interest; and *qualities*, which alludes to availability to rethink possess values and those of expert figures.

Figure 1: Research Model

DATA ANALYSIS

Table 1 exhibits the level of emotional intelligence of public elementary teachers in Caraga Region. The overall mean of 4.00 was described as *high*. The high level could be attributed to the high rating given by the respondents in 4 of the indicators and *very high* on *motivation*. This means that the responses of the emotional intelligence of Public Elementary School Teachers in Caraga Region was manifested in majority of the cases in terms of motivation, empathy, self-awareness, self-regulation, and social skills. The cited overall mean score was the result gathered from the computed mean scores of 4.33 or *very high*, motivation, 3.99 or *high*, empathy, and 3.97 or *high* on self-awareness.

Table 1. Level of Emotional Intelligence of Teachers

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Self-awareness	0.76	3.97	High
Self-regulation	0.52	3.94	High
Motivation	0.59	4.33	Very High
Empathy	0.69	3.99	High
Social Skills	0.55	3.79	High
Overall	0.44	4.00	High

Shown in Table 2 are the data on the level of teaching competency of public elementary school teachers in Caraga Region which gathered an over-all mean of 4.24 or *very high* descriptive level. Results revealed that majority of the teachers are competent in *managerial* with a mean of 4.28, followed by *planning* with a mean of 4.24, *evaluation* 4.27, and *planning* 4.24.skills. The over-all mean score of the level of teaching competency of public elementary school teachers in Caraga Region were computed based on the mean of all the indicators.

Table 2. Level of Teaching Competency of Teachers

Indicators	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
Planning	0.53	4.24	Very High
Presentation	0.49	4.19	High
Evaluation	0.56	4.27	Very High
Managerial	0.52	4.28	Very High
Overall	0.43	4.24	Very High

Shown in Table 3 is the level of *Openness to Experience* of Public Elementary School Teachers in Caraga Region with the over-all mean of 4.05 described as *high*. The cited over-all mean is taken from all the items in level of openness to experience is taken of public elementary school teachers in Caraga Region. Results revealed that the mean score is manifested majority of the teachers.

The grand mean scores were computed based on the mean of all the items. The item with the highest mean is *curious about many different things* 4.24 described as *very high*, *is original, comes up with new ideas*, 4.21 *very high*, other indicators having a mean ranging from 4.18 to 3.77 are also described as high. The item with the highest mean is *curious about many different things* 4.24 described as *very high*, *is original, comes up with new ideas*, 4.21 *very high*, other indicators having a mean ranging from 4.18 to 3.77 are also described as *high*.

Table 3. Level of Openness to Experience of Teachers

Items	SD	Mean	Descriptive Level
<i>Seeing oneself as someone who:</i>			
Is original, comes up with new ideas	0.65	4.21	Very High
Is curious about many different things	0.66	4.24	Very High
Is ingenious, a deep thinker	0.65	4.04	High
Has an active imagination	0.69	4.14	High
Is inventive	0.69	3.90	High
Value artistic, aesthetic experiences	0.72	4.09	High
Prefers work that is routine	0.64	4.18	High
Likes to reflect, play with ideas	0.65	4.12	High
Has few artistic interest	0.78	3.81	High
Is sophisticated in art music or literature	0.70	3.77	High
Overall	.48	4.05	High

Reflected in Table 4 are the data on the results of correlations between emotional intelligence and teaching competency of Public Elementary School Teachers in Caraga Region. The overall r-value is .516 with $p < 0.05$. Showing that emotional intelligence has significant relationship with teaching competency of teachers. This leads to the rejection of the null hypothesis which states that there is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and teaching competency of public elementary school teachers in Caraga Region.

Examining closely the correlation among the indicators of the two variables, it could be seen in Table 4 that the r- values ranged from .113 to .492 with $p < 0.05$. These r- values had contributed to the significant overall correlation of the two main variables. It could be noted that among the indicators of emotional intelligence, *motivation* obtained the highest r- value of $r = .528$, $p < 0.05$ when correlated with teaching

competency. On the other hand, *social skills* is the second highest with an r-value of $r = .437$, $p < 0.05$ also significant. It is followed by *empathy* with an r value of ($r = .385$, $p < 0.05$) having also a significant correlation.

Table 4. Correlations between Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Competency

Emotional Intelligence	Teaching Competency				
	Planning	Presentation	Evaluation	Managerial	Overall
Self-Awareness	.189*** (.000)	.189*** (.000)	.166** (.001)	.113* (.023)	.199*** (.000)
Self-Regulation	.317*** (.000)	.329*** (.000)	.198*** (.000)	.284*** (.000)	.339*** (.000)
Motivation	.492*** (.000)	.447*** (.000)	.378*** (.000)	.429*** (.000)	.528*** (.000)
Empathy	.281*** (.000)	.365*** (.000)	.294*** (.000)	.339*** (.000)	.385*** (.000)
Social Skills	.301*** (.000)	.392*** (.000)	.370*** (.000)	.384*** (.000)	.437*** (.000)
Overall	.431*** (.000)	.471*** (.000)	.387*** (.000)	.420*** (.000)	.516*** (.000)

Table 5 views the relationship between openness to experience and teaching competency. The constructs of teaching competency being the dependent variable are planning, presentation, evaluation and managerial. At 0.05 level of significance, the overall r-value of .535 indicated a significant relationship between openness to experience and teaching competency. Thus, this result led to the rejection of the null hypothesis.

Analyzing closely the correlation of openness to experience with the indicators of teaching competency, it showed that openness to experience registered the highest r-value when it was correlated with managerial ($r = .529$, $p < 0.05$). Correlation with presentation showed an r-value of .483 at $p < 0.05$. The lowest correlation is with evaluation ($r = .464$) but still significant at $p < 0.05$

Table 5. Correlations between Openness to Experience and Teaching Competency

Teaching Competency	Openness to Experience
Planning	.298*** (.000)
Presentation	.483*** (.000)
Evaluation	.464*** (.000)
Managerial	.529*** (.000)
Overall	.535*** (.000)

To determine the significance of the moderating effect of openness to experience on the relationship between emotional intelligence and teaching competency of teachers in Caraga Region hierarchical regression analysis was done for the purpose. This is reflected in Table 6 as the source of data for Table 7 and 8 which are both needed for the mod graph in Figure 3.

The moderating effect was premised on the idea that the higher is the level of openness to experience of teachers the higher is the effect of emotional intelligence on his/her work as compared to those with lower level of openness to experience. Openness to experience was the moderating variable, emotional intelligence was the

independent variable and teaching competency was the dependent variable. The emotional intelligence variable was multiplied with the openness to experience variable to produce an interaction term. The two main effects and the interaction term (emotional intelligence x Openness to Experience) were used in a hierarchical regression to predict teaching competency of teachers in Caraga Region.

In regressing emotional intelligence and openness to experience in the step 2 regressions, the model was observed to be significant ($p < 0.05$) and demonstrated a change in R-square of .113. The R square change tells how much variance in the Teaching Competency these predictors explained in each step. The R –square change of .113 means an additional variance of 11% to the variance of 27% in the step 1 regression showing that 27% of the variance in teaching competency of teachers is due to the openness to experience by itself. The interaction term explained about 0.5% new variance above and beyond the two main effects.

Table 6. Hierarchical Regression to Assess the Moderating Effect of Openness to Experience on Emotional Intelligence-to-Teaching Competency Relationship

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig	R Square Change
	B	Std. Error	Beta			
Step 1						.266
(Constant)	2.236	.168		13.297	.000	
Emotional Intelligence	.501	.042	.516	12.010	.000	
Step 2						.113
(Constant)	1.535	.175		8.746	.000	
Emotional Intelligence	.332	.043	.342	7.682	.000	
Openness to Experience	.340	.040	.378	8.499	.000	
Step3						.018
(Constant)	-2.693	1.244		-2.165	.031	
Emotional Intelligence	1.396	.313	1.436	4.464	.000	
Openness to Experience	1.375	.304	1.530	4.522	.000	
Emotional Intelligence by Openness to Experience	-.259	.075	-1.923	-3.433	.001	

This was stamped not as much as the adjustment in R-square observed in step 1 and 2. Interestingly, the ANOVA was significant ($p < .05$) recommending that the collaboration impact was a supporter of the model difference.

Looking at Table 6, a significant main effect for openness to experience was obtained ($B = 1.530$, $p < 0.05$) and it signified that those with higher openness to experience have higher level of teaching competency. Recommending that the collaboration impact was a supporter of the model difference. ($B = -.923$, $p < .05$) which was graphed in Figure 3. To have the modgraph, the unstandardized coefficients of the interaction term in step 3 regression in Table 6 was utilized and displayed in Table 8, supported with the descriptive statistics of each variable and the computed values of the main effects of emotional intelligence and openness to experience on teaching competency in Table 7.

The Figure 3 shows that those with high openness to experience manifested a steeper slope between emotional intelligence and teaching competency than those with low openness to experience, rejecting the null hypothesis.

It can be stated therefore, that openness to experience significantly moderates the relationship between emotional intelligence and teaching competency of public elementary school teachers in Caraga Region

DISCUSSION

Emotional Intelligence of Public Elementary Teachers

It is generally shown that the level of emotional intelligence of public elementary school teachers in Caraga Region in terms of *motivation* was rated by the respondents as very high. This means that teacher's emotional intelligence is always manifested in practicing their profession. Teachers tend to see self-growth and development as a never-ending process the reason why they love self-development activities because they wanted to feel developed even when they get older. This also means that teachers wanted to improve more not only for any outer acknowledgment but rather on account of the fulfillment from going for and accomplishing elevated requirements.

Moreover, this could also mean that teachers feel really passionate about how things are done and feel totally engaged with their work. This is in consonance with the findings of Mortiboys (2005), which cited there are sure qualities of a sincerely clever instructor that can be identified. An instructor dedicates a lot of vitality to make an empowering climate in the classroom and considers the students' emotions. He or she ought to be a specialist at tuning in; pay attention to the learner's expectations; devotion to learner's excitement in the showing procedure and apply a remarkable way to deal with their calling to have the capacity to set up an amicable association with their understudies.

Another indicator of the level of emotional intelligence of public elementary school teachers is *empathy* which the respondents rated a high response. The high level could be attributed to the respondents' affirmation that being a good listener, listening mindfully and being consciously mindful of what isn't being stated, being circumspect of other individuals' inclination notwithstanding when they may have accomplished something that causes issue, and having the capacity to assemble a decent group and having the capacity to achieve accord while being testing and steady. This is in relation to the proposition of Edannur (2010) which posited that emotional intelligence of educators is required with the goal that learning happens ideally and enhances to the most extreme learning. Likewise, the findings are in congruence with the study of Nicolini (2010) that taking care of understudies' feelings is undisputable that their feeling life must be set up in order to decidedly affect understudies' scholastic execution. Further, teachers should dissect their emotional abilities solitary at that point continue to grow understudy's enthusiastic education.

This supports the findings of Palmer and Stough (2001) which affirmed that emotional intelligence at the point when connected to the working environment includes the empathy to viably see, express, comprehend and oversee feelings in an expert and compelling way at work.

One more indicator which displays a high response is *self-awareness*. This means that emotional intelligence is manifested oftentimes. The high level also means that teachers are aware of how behavior affects others and aware of the responses of others to what I say and do, knowing what the deepest values are and living by them and turning down work that in conflicts with those values, and being very much in touch with feelings. This implies that emotional self-awareness precedes all stages of emotional intelligence developmental ability and could be the basic foundation which behavior germinates and that one's own emotions recognizing their impact to guide decision (Singh, 2010).

Teaching Competency of Public Elementary Teachers

The dependent variable considered on this study is the level of teaching competency of teachers which was rated by the respondents as *very high*. One measure of the teacher's competency is *managerial* functions in which the respondents rated very high. This could be attributed that teachers are imposing classroom discipline being maintained in the class: teachers instructions that were not identified with the substance being taken after and both going to and non-going to practices of the students are being perceived; going to conduct being compensated, bearings being given to wipe out non-going to practices, questions being request to check understudies going to conduct, students emotions and thoughts being acknowledged, and non-verbal prompts being utilized to perceive students going to and non-going to practices.

The result can be seen through the words of Ganaie and Mudasir (2014) who mentioned in their study that teachers can shape the entire world but teachers be sufficiently skillful to think of the desire for the general public. In addition, Pratibha (2017), stipulated that the term competency is a description of those exhibitions that depend on the securing, coordination, composite building and use of an arrangement of related ability and information.

Evaluation, the next highest indicator, also generated a very high descriptive level. The result was attributed to the factors that understudies advance towards the targets of the exercise being checked and the strategies of the assessment being proper: significant to the goals, substantial, solid and goal. Besides, student's troubles in comprehension or rule being analyzed well-ordered addressing and appropriate healing measures were undertaken by teachers. The findings is conformed the results of the study of Kulkarni (2011) and Tyagi (2013), which accepted evaluation and managerial as deemed necessary to show teaching competency.

Openness to Experience of Teachers

It is observed that the items of *openness to experience* of public elementary school teachers in Caraga Region demonstrated an overall descriptive level of high which means that openness to experience is always manifested. This signifies that openness to experience implies teachers are curious about many different thing, is original and comes up with new ideas, and prefers to work that is routine.

In fact, in the studies of Kaufman (2013) and Swami and Furnham (2014), they expressed that individuals high in openness to feelings encounter a more extensive scope of feelings, acknowledge their feelings and experience complex feelings all the more frequently. Furthermore, Menninghaus, Wagner, Hanich and Jacobsen (2014) expressed that a man who is high in openness to experience is imaginative, adaptable, inquisitive and brave. He appreciates having his psyche and faculties animated, for example, by review craftsmanship, tuning in to new music, inspecting outlandish cooking and perusing writing and verse.

Correlations between Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Competency of Public Elementary School Teachers in Caraga Region

The overall result on the correlation of the constructs reveals that emotional intelligence is significantly related to planning, presentation, evaluation and managerial competence of public elementary teachers in Caraga Region. In the holistic point of view, emotional intelligence is positively associated to teaching competency and therefore rejects the null hypothesis that there is no significant relationship between emotional intelligence and teaching competency.

The result of the study concluded by Pathak (2016), that of teacher emotional intelligence affects significantly to their teaching competency or in other words,

teacher trainees belonging to high, average and low emotional intelligence group differ significantly in terms of teaching competency. Therefore, concluded that emotional intelligence is necessity for teacher competency.

As mention by the study of Rajalaksmi and Shirlin (2017), if they develop the emotional competencies, which thusly enable them to build up the same among their understudies. Training competency in instructing can be create in educators by methods for enthusiastic insight. (Tulo & Gempes, 2016) Mediating Effect of Training Perspective It is along these lines most essential for understudy educator to build up the emotional intelligence to end up a flawless instructor.

Correlation between Openness to Experience and Teaching Competency of Public Elementary school Teachers in Caraga Region

Openness to experience and teaching competency obtain a positive correlation demonstrated in the overall result. This portrays a significant relationship between these two constructs. Additionally, this reveals that there is a significant relationship between openness to experience and teaching competency. Hence, this study aims to prove that openness to experience has significant relation with teaching competency.

The result of the study were presented by Ganjeh (2010), which stated that openness to experience is a proportion of profundity, broadness and fluctuation in a man's creative ability and desire for understanding. The factor identifies with insightfulness, receptiveness to new thoughts, social interests, instructive aptitudes and inventiveness and also an enthusiasm for shifted tangible and subjective encounters, of which in this study related to teaching competency.

Moderating Effect of Openness to Experience on the Relationship between Emotional Intelligence and Teaching Competency of Teachers in Caraga Region

The results reveal that emotional intelligence predicts teaching competency and openness to experience also predicts teaching competency. To validate the existence of the moderation analysis, a ModGraph program (Jose, 2013) was utilized and facilitated to compute the cell means and generate its significant interaction for the graphical display. This allowed further information processing from the regression analysis to visually examine the statistical interactions. The graph (see figure 2) proves that openness to experience significantly moderates the relationship between emotional intelligence and teaching competency. This means that emotional intelligence with higher openness to experience do enforce higher level of teacher competency as compared to those with lower emotional intelligence.

Since the effect is higher at higher level, a significant moderating effect occurred as the rule implied that such interaction would exist when the graphs would have different gradients as well as the slope and the lines should not be in parallel according to Aiken and West (1991) and Jose (2008). Such effect would have a significant interaction (Stevens, 2000) when lines do not cross and that the slope of the lines are not in parallel in an ordinal interaction given enough statistical power. This moderating relationship may be considered as a new contribution to the body of knowledge especially that combining these constructs in a single study is relatively sparse in the academic literature.

In addition, Mohan and Mulla (2013), tried to figure out the relationship between openness and job complexity. The researcher herein refers the job complexity to teaching competency. It is seen that people that are more open will be disappointed in occupations low in ability assortment was concluded that there is a significant and positive correlation between emotional intelligence and teaching competency. Moreover the study of Vengatesan and Jayachandran (2016), found out that emotional intelligence is decidedly identified with teacher self-competency. High openness demonstrates that an individual will be more prompted in to his condition and will be mindful to different impacts while taking choices and this includes the choice to be competent or not.

CONCLUSION

The after effect of the investigation shows that the level of emotional intelligence of elementary teachers in Caraga Region prove to be high. More so, the level of teacher competency manifests a very high indication.

Openness to experience, another construct, also yields a high implication. On the other hand, the correlation between emotional intelligence and teacher competency purports a significant relationship thus rejecting the null hypothesis. Similarly, a significant relationship also exists when emotional intelligence and teachers competency are correlated pointing to the rejection of the null hypothesis also. Likewise, openness to experience significantly moderates the relationship between emotional intelligence and teacher competency.

Based from the findings of this investigation, the proposition of Mayer and Salovey (2013) has much to offer to this study on emotional intelligence as it supports the very significant relationship between emotional intelligence and teacher competency wherein the behavior of teachers are shaped by various experience and training. Further, teachers also engage in some teacher competency coming from anticipated rewards. The expected gains in reputation are just some of the benefits that would motivate people to engage in a teaching field. Moreover, the result of the study support the idea that there is also significant relationship between openness to experience and teaching competency (Oakes, Ferris, Martocchio, Buckley, & Broach, 2001). On the whole the ultimate aim of the study has proven that openness to experience significantly moderates the relationship between emotional intelligence and teaching competency of teachers.

REFERENCES

- i. Aiken, L.S., & West, S.G. (1991). *Multiple regression: Testing and interpreting interactions*. Sage.
- ii. Al-Sharif, E.M. (2010). *Evaluation of student / teacher teaching competencies in the curricula and teaching methods of motor expression in the light of quality academic standards*. *World Journal of Sport Sciences* 3 (S): 331- 358, 2010 ISSN 2078-4724
- iii. Andrew, M.D., & Schwab, R.L. (1995). *Has reform in teacher education influenced teacher performance? an outcome assessment of graduates of an eleven university consortium*. *Action in Teacher education*, 17(3), 43-53
- iv. Barr, A.S. (1952). *Chapter 1: The measurement of teacher characteristics and prediction of teaching efficiency*. *Review of Educational Research*, 22(3), 169-174.
- v. Conner, T.S., & Silvia, P.J. (2015). *Creative days: a daily diary study of emotions, personality, and everyday creativity*. *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 9(4), 463.
- vi. Cucu-Ciuhan, G., & Raban-Motounu, N. (2012). *The openness to experience questionnaire: construction and validation*. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences* 33 (2012) 717 – 721
- vii. Darling-Hammond, L. (1999). *Teacher quality and student achievement*. *Education policy analysis archives*, 8, 1.
- viii. Dollinger, S.J., Leong, F.T., & Ulicni, S.K. (1996). *On traits and values: With special reference to openness to experience*. *Journal of Research in Personality*, 30, 23–44.
- ix. Edannur, S. (2010). *Emotional intelligence of teacher educators*. *International Journal of Education Science*, 2(2): 115–121.
- x. *Encyclopaedic Dictionary of Education* (1997). Mehndiratta, M.ND! Sarup and sons.
- xi. Erden, E.M.I.N.E. (2010). *Problems that preschool teachers face in the curriculum implementation*. *Dissertation-M.Ed. Middle East: Middle East Technical University*.
- xii. Ganjeh, S.J. (2010). *The relationship of personality characteristics and burnout among nurses*. *Iranian Journal of Nursing and Midwifery Research*, 14(4).
- xiii. Ganaie, M.Y., & Mudasir, H.A. (2014). *A Comparative study of teaching competency of secondary school teachers in district Srinagar*. *Rep Opinion* 2014; 6(6):49-54]. (ISSN: 1553-9873)
- xiv. Goad, D. (2005). *Emotional intelligence and teacher retention*. *Unpublished raw data presented at the 2005 Institute on Emotional Intelligence, Texas A&M University Kingsville, Kingsville, TX*.
- xv. Goleman, D. (1995). *Emotional intelligence: Why it can matter more than IQ*. London: Bloomsbury.
- xvi. Goleman, D. (1998). *Working with emotional intelligence*. New York: Bantam
- xvii. Goleman, D. (2006). *Emotional Intelligence*. New York: A Division of Random House, Inc.
- xviii. Goleman, D. (2013). *Primal leadership: Unleashing the power of emotional intelligence*. Harvard Business Press. *Journal of Applied Behavioral Science*, 24; 37.

- xix. Jose, P. E. (2013). *Modgraph-1: A programme to compute cell means for the graphical display of moderating analyses: the internet version, version 3.0.* Wellington: Victoria University Wellington, 2013.
- xx. Kaufman, S.B. (2013). *Opening up openness to experience: A four-factor model and relations to creative achievement in the arts and sciences.* *The Journal of Creative Behavior*, 47(4), 233-255.
- xxi. Khatkar, Sangwan & Bedi (2016). *A Study of teaching competency of prospective teachers in relation to their emotional intelligence.* *International Journal of Enhanced Research in Educational Development (IJERED)* ISSN: 2320-8708, Vol. 4 Issue 2, March-April, 2016, Impact Factor: 1.554
- xxii. King, S.H., & Watson, A. (2010). *Teaching excellence for all our students.* *Theory Into Practice*, 49(3), 175-184.
- xxiii. Kulkarni, B. (2011). *Relationship between teaching competence and attitudes towards teaching of B.Ed. trained teachers working in upgraded primary schools.* *International referred research Journal*, 3(30).
- xxiv. Liakopoulou, M. (2011). *The Professional competence of teachers: which qualities, attitudes, skills and knowledge contribute to a teacher's effectiveness?* *International Journal of Humanities and Social Science*. Vol. 1 No. 21 [Special Issue - December 2011] 66
- xxv. Mayer, P., & Salovey, J.D. (1993). *The intelligence of emotional intelligence.* *Intelligence*, 17, 433-442.
- xxvi. McCrae, R.R. (1992). *Openness to experience as a basic dimension of personality.* Paper presented at the annual convention of American Psychological Association. Washington D.C.
- xxvii. McCrae, R.R. (1993-1994). *Openness to experience as a basic dimension of personality.* *Imagination, Cognition and Personality*, 13, 39-55.
- xxviii. McCrae, R.R. (1994). *Openness to experience: expanding the boundaries of factor V.* *European Journal of Personality*, 8(4), 251-272.
- xxix. McCrae, R.R., & Costa, P.T. (2008). *The five-factor theory of personality.* In O. P. John, R. W. Robins, L. A. Pervin (Eds.), *Handbook of personality: Theory and research* (3rd ed.; pp. 159-181). New York, NY: Guilford Press
- xxx. McCrae, R.R., & Sutin, A.R. (2009). *Openness to experience.* *Handbook of individual differences in social behavior*, 15, 257-273. McKenzie, N. (2007). *Teaching excellence awards: An apple for the teacher?* *Australian Journal of Education*, 51 no2: 190-204.
- xxxi. Menninghaus, W., Wagner, V., Hanich, J., & Jacobsen, T. (2014). *Art schema effects on affective experience: The case of disgusting images.* *Psychology of Aesthetics, Creativity, and the Arts*, 8(2), 120. Medley, M. (1982). *Teacher effectiveness*, in Mitzel, H.E. *Encyclopedia of Educational Research*, New York: The Free Press
- xxxii. Mohan, G., & Mulla, Z.R. (2013). *Openness to experience and work outcomes: exploring the moderating effects of conscientiousness and Job complexity.* *Great Lakes Herald*. Page 18, Vol 7, No 2, September 2013. Tata Institute of Social Sciences, Mumbai
- xxxiii. Moore, S., & Nyiel, K. (2007). *Retrospective insights on teaching: exploring teaching excellence through the eyes of the alumni.* *Journal of Further & Higher Education*, 31 (2), 133-143.
- xxxiv. Mortiboys, A. (2005). *Teaching with Emotional Intelligence: A step-by-step guide for higher and further education professionals.* New York: Routledge.
- xxxv. Nettle, D. (2009). *Personality: what makes you the way you are.* New York, NY: Oxford University Press.
- xxxvi. Neubert, A. (2004). *The five-factor model of personality in the workplace.* *Journal of Applied Psychology*, 89, 610-621. Rochester Institute of Technology
- xxxvii. Nicolini, P. (2010). *Training teachers to observation: An approach through multiple intelligences theory.* *Bulletin of the Transilvania University of Brasov.*, 3(52) 91-98.
- xxxviii. Oakes, D.W., Ferris, G.R., Martocchio, J.J., Buckley, M.R., & Broach, D. (2001). *Cognitive ability and personality predictors of training program skill acquisition and job performance.* *Journal of Business and Psychology*, 15(4), 523-548.
- xxxix. Palmer, P. J. & Coldwell, G. (2000). *Paradoxes in teaching and Learning*

- xl. Palmer, B., & Stough, C. (2001). *Emotional intelligence and effective leadership*. *Leadership & Organization Development Journal*, 22(1), 5-10.
- xli. Pathak, R. (2016). *Effect of emotional intelligence of teacher trainees on their teaching competency*. *Electronic International Interdisciplinary Research Journal (EIIRJ) ISSN 2277-8721 Bi-monthly Vol V Issues I Reviewed Journal Jan/Feb-2016*
- xlii. Pratibha, R. (2017). *Teaching competency of primary School Teachers in relation to their sex and educational qualification*. *Abhinav National Monthly Refereed Journal of Research in Arts & Education*. Abhinav Publication. Volume 6, Issue 1 (January) ISSN-2277-1182
- xlili. Rajalakshmi & Shirlin, P. (2017). *Emotional intelligence and teaching competency of B.Ed. students in Kanyakumari District*. *International Journal of Research Granthaalayah*, 5(3) SE, 40-46. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.54596>
- xliv. Rana, V.R. (2013). *A study of teaching competence in pre and post training of B.Ed. trainees in relation to their rank difference in entrance test*. *Educational Confab* ISSN: 2320-009X
- xlv. Shepard, K., Harland, T., Stein, S., & Tidswell, T. (2011). *Preparing an application for a higher-education teaching-excellence award: whose foot fits Cinderella's shoe?* *Journal of Higher Education Policy & Management*, 33, no1: 47-56.
- xlvi. Singh, K. (2010). *Developing human capital by linking emotional intelligence with personal competencies in Indian business organizations*. *International Journal of Business Science and Applied Management*, 5(2), 29-42
- xlvii. Swami, V., & Furnham, A. (2014). *Personality and aesthetics*. In P.P.L. Tinio & J.K. Smith (Eds), *The Cambridge Handbook of the Psychology of Aesthetics and the Arts* (pp.540-561). Cambridge, UK: Cambridge University Press.
- xlviii. Thiessen, D. (2011). *Innovation in teacher education: A review of recent literature*. Toronto: MGS Publication Services.
- xliv. Tyagi (2013). *A study of teaching effectiveness of secondary school teachers in relation to their demographic characteristics*. *International Journal of Engineering and Innovative Technology (IJEIT)*, Vol. 3, Issue 1, July 2013.
- l. Valcárcel, M., Cases, M.V., & de Castro, MDL. (2003). *La preparación del profesorado Universitario Español para la Convergencia*. *Europea en Educación Superior Estudio*, EA2003-0040 MECED.
- li. Vengatesan, R., & Jayachandran, V. (2016). *A study of classroom performance of teacher-trainees of DIET Colleges in relation certain social, psychological variables of various regions in Andhra Pradesh*. Lulu.com.
- lii. Villa & Poblete (Dir.) 2007. *Aprendizaje basado en competencias*. Bilbao: Universidad de Deusto/Mensajero.
- liii. Weisinger, H. (1998). *Emotional intelligence at work*. San Francisco, California: Jossey-Bass
- liv. Woody, F. (2010) *Teaching excellence award winners*. *Teaching of Psychology*, 37, no4: 229-236.